

STUDENT CENTRIC LEARNING THROUGH PLANNED HARDWORK - AN INNOVATIVE MODEL

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Abstract:

The strategies followed by educational institutions and the students become very important when the performance of students in the examinations is concerned. By means of properly planned and well guided model of training and motivation to do hard work, students can follow a well disciplined study plan and become exceptionally successful in examinations. Teaching and training by experienced and dedicated faculty members, continuous support by parents and motivating the students based on setting their goal through proper career guidance and orienting them to focus on the study are few motivating factors in a planned systematic accelerated study model. It is found that instead of studying at last minutes for the exams, if students continuously study everyday through hard work and with the proper plan, they can do a better performance. In this paper, we have discussed the strategies the students should adopt during such transition of the curriculum, the importance of Pre-university education in deciding the career of a student, Opportunities in intermediate education, challenges in intermediate education, plan of study etc. The paper also contains the strategies the parents of such students to be followed based on changing family environment, parents dream, expectations, pressure, and worry. To face such critical situation, and support the students and the parents, Expert Pre-University College in Mangalore, India, developed a new innovative hard-work based training model called Seven to Seven (12 hours) Training Model. In the environment of enhanced competition, this new model is Student Centric. The paper contains the Core values of this new model, SWOC analysis, ABCD analysis, Stakeholders expectations, Institutional expectations, Student expectation, Teachers expectations and Parents expectations as a Case Study.

Index Terms: Innovation in Intermediate Education, Seven To Seven Study Model, SWOC Analysis & ABCD Analysis

1. Introduction:

Innovations in higher educational system covered long way and its contribution improved the quality of education and quality of graduates [1-2]. Several studies on innovations and quality in higher education including Strategic Planning in Higher Education Institutions [3], Innovations and Best Practices can Transform Higher Education Institutions [4], quality in higher education [5-6], Internal Quality Assurance Cell and its Contribution [7], Enhancement of Graduate attributes in Higher Education Institutions through Stage Models [8], Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions [9], Effective Leadership and Governance [10], Strategy Development and Deployment in Higher Education Institutions [11], Faculty Empowerment Strategies in Higher Education Institutions [12], Unique & Successful Model in Integrated Development [13], Applying SWOC Analysis to an Institution of Higher Education [14], Techniques for Electric Energy Auditing in Education System [15], Societal Expectation And Institutional Accountability in Higher Education [16], Methods and Approaches for Employability Skill Generation in Higher Educational Institutions [17], Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions through Best Practices in Library [18], Analysis of Academic Administrative System Implemented in Higher educational institution [19], Learning through Team Centric Exercise & Key Point Pedagogy - An

effective Learning Model for Slow Learners in Higher Education Training [20], Opportunities and Challenges for Private Universities [21], Innovations in Private Universities [22], Creating Innovators through setting up organizational Vision, Mission and Core Values : a Strategic Model in Higher Education [23], Comparative Study on MBA Programmes in Private & Public Universities [24], Impact of On-line Education on Higher Education System [25], Innovations in Higher Education - A new model implemented in MCA degree programme [26], Environmental Consciousness in Higher Educational Institutions [27], Analysis of Choice Based Credit System in Higher Education [28], Innovations in Student Centric Learning – A Study of Top Business Schools [29], Innovations in Experimental Learning – A Study of World Top Business Schools [30], How to Increase Research Productivity in Higher Educational Institutions [31], Academic Support through Information System [32], and Quality Teaching and Learning as Practice Within Different Disciplinary Discourses [33], Innovative Education Model to realize Ideal Education System [34], ABCD analysis of Stage Model in Higher Education [35],) Analysis of NAAC Accreditation System using ABCD framework [36], Application of ABCD Analysis Framework on Private University System [37], The Study of New National Institutional Ranking System using ABCD Framework [38], ABC Model of Research Productivity and Higher Educational Institutional Ranking [39], Smart Library Model for Future Generations [40], Green Education Concepts & Strategies in Higher Education Model [41], Hitting Two Birds with One Stone : Srinivas University B.Com. Model in Corporate Auditing [42], Quality Enhancement in Office Management of Higher Education Institutions through Innovations & Best Practices[43], Academic Support through Information System [44], Changing Approaches in Campus Placements - A new futuristic Model [45], Information Technology Innovations in Library Management [46], Teaching - Learning Process in Higher Education Institutions [47], Maintaining Teacher Quality in Higher Education Institutions [48], Student performance and Learning Outcomes in Higher Education Institutions [49], Catering Student Enrollment and Retaining Diversity in Higher Education Institutions [50], Student Evaluation and Reforms in Higher Education Institutions [51] are studied and published.

Apart from the above innovations in higher education system, it is also possible to provide new innovative model based on hard work for longer period of a day by keeping the students in the college to prepare them to face the examination confidently. In this paper, we have discussed the efforts and strategies required by students, parents, educational institutions and teachers to improve the examination performance of students in order to provide a rosy career based on their dream. We have also discussed the strategies the students should adopt during such transition of the curriculum, the importance of Pre-university education in deciding the career of a student, Opportunities in intermediate education, challenges in intermediate education, plan of study etc. The paper also contains the strategies the parents of such students to be followed based on changing family environment, parents dream, expectations, pressure, and worry. To face such critical situation, and support the students and the parents, Expert Pre-University College in Mangalore developed a new innovative hard-work based training model called Seven to Seven (12 hours) Training Model. In the environment of enhanced competition, this new model is Student Centric. The paper contains the Core values of this new model, SWOC analysis, ABCD analysis, Stakeholders expectations, Institutional expectations, Student expectation, Teachers expectations and Parents expectations as a Case Study.

2. Consequence of Common Curriculum & Evaluation System in the Country:

Recently, Karnataka Pre-University Board has introduced the National Core Curriculum along with NCERT textbooks to science stream in pre-university education as per National policy of common syllabus in the country. The NCERT curriculum is comparatively tough for students studied their previous education in regional languages as well as in State Govt. syllabus and adopting for such common syllabus made them fearful to choose science stream in intermediate courses. Based on the national education policy of the country, every student irrespective of their state, have to study common syllabus in 11th and 12th standards and have to qualify in a common entrance exam conducted to technical courses admission as well as Medical and Dental courses admission. As a result, the students who have studied their high school education in respective State syllabus find the common Central syllabus very difficult due to its advanced level of analysis of the topics, especially in science & mathematics stream. But is proved that the students can get rid of such fear and perform well in examinations by means of properly planned and well guided hard work.

3. Efforts of Central & State Governments & Education System:

The Indian government is making considerable efforts to support higher secondary education in the country. It has directed its State governments to develop and provide the electronic copy of all textbooks from the first standard to the twelfth standard free of cost from their Education department website. The central government also arranged free online distribution of NCERT books for every student of the country [52]. As a result, in spite of economic and regional disparities, every student of the country has free access to textbooks prepared as per national curriculum. The efforts of Central government and State governments in providing quality higher secondary education in the country is listed below:

(i) Free Online Downloadable Books: The National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) has a scheme on preparing CBSE books in electronic form from the 1st standard to 12th standard in English, Hindi, and Urdu languages from its website. These books can be stored in Android, IOP, or Windows platform and read using the mobile phone, tablets, or computers. Similarly, all state governments also provide their textbooks for the 1st standard to 12th standard in pdf electronic form to download freely from their Education board website for public students use.

(ii) Question Bank with Answer: In order to help the students and remove examination fear, the State government also prepares question bank along with answers for each chapter in all subjects of the 10th, 11th and 12th standard classes due to the fact that in these classes, the students have to qualify public exams and Common Entrance examinations for getting admission to professional courses. Apart from that the NCERTI also prepared model question papers for CBSE for 10th and 12th standard to guide the format of public examination question papers.

(iii) Exemplar Books for Intelligent Hard Workers: Along with the general textbooks, NCERT also supplies exemplar books in science and mathematics subject for 11th and 12th standard students. These books contain problems on applied nature and also multiple choice questions related to the topics of each chapter. The exemplar books help intelligent students to apply their intelligence to crack such exemplar problems.

(iv) Satellite-Based Lectures: Training through satellite broadband technology allows rural communities to experience the same level of education and services that are within urban centres. Satellite connectivity can be delivered anywhere in the country or across the globe. With no wires needed, the satellite is quick to deploy wherever the school or training centre is located. Satellite is cost-effective for education and

training. Utilizing satellite enables videoconferencing, live lectures via telephone and even real-time collaborative tools, such as a digital whiteboard where content can be modified in real time, all at a low cost. Different projects are successfully launched in collaboration with both government and private agencies to train students of both 10th and 12th standard to prepare them for various competitive exams in different states of India.

(v) Free TV based Entrance Exam Trainings: State Governments telecasting training programmes for 12th standard students to take Common Entrance Exam (CET) for joining professional courses. For example, Karnataka Government is arranging such programmes in its TV channel in the name of Vikasana Series every year through Karnataka Examination Authority (KEA) which is a capacity building programme to empower CET students. The study materials of this training programme can be downloadable free of cost from KEA website. The telecast video lectures are also downloadable from KEA website for later and further use [53].

4. Efforts Required for Success:

The skills and efforts required by the students to develop national level competency in changing environment & curriculum structure are putting pressure on higher secondary educational institutions and its stakeholders. The responsibility and challenges faced by students, teachers, parents, and institutions in this changing environment

(i) Students Responsibility & Challenges:

- ✓ To compete at national level in the given common curriculum, plan your study and do very hard work.
- ✓ Download study materials available in NCERT website and each chapter carefully. Solve all exercise problems yourself by refereeing sample problems solved in the chapters.
- ✓ Choosing a college where the teachers have experience in teaching the subjects and interact with the teachers

(ii) Faculty Responsibility & Challenges:

- ✓ Setting the goal of every student.
- ✓ Nurturing them to focus on their goal through set target.
- ✓ Building the confidence in each and every student.
- ✓ Motivating them to achieve the maximum from them.
- ✓ Develop a strategy to train the students effectively and make them work hard.
- ✓ Monitoring them continuously.
- ✓ Evaluate at each stage.
- ✓ Prepare both for board examination and competitive examinations.
- ✓ Fix accountability through competitive offers.

(iii) Parents Responsibility & Challenges:

- ✓ Identify the interest of your child.
- ✓ Admit them to a college which has objectives to nurture its students.
- ✓ Since the marks of 11th and 12th standards decide the future education of the children, admit them to a college which maintains strict discipline and innovative model of teaching and learning by making them do hard work.

(iv) Organizational Responsibility & Challenges:

- ✓ Teaching and training by experienced and dedicated faculty members.
- ✓ Continuous support and motivating the students based on setting their goal through proper career guidance.

- ✓ Orienting the students to focus on the study is the major solution during this transition of the curriculum.
- ✓ In such transition, instead of studying for last minutes for the exams, if students continuously study every day through hard work and with the proper plan, they can do a better performance.

5. Strategies to be adopted by Stakeholders:

5.1 Strategies to be adopted by the Students: Students should adopt following strategies during such transition of curriculum from the state level to the national level.

- ✓ Choose a good college which has a long tradition in training students systematically using an innovative model, experienced faculty members, and providing printed study materials to the students.
- ✓ Choose a college which has the residential facility and focuses on hard work from both students and teachers.
- ✓ Collect study materials and question bank of all subjects of the course from various internet sites of both Education department and free charity sites.
- ✓ Preparing own question answer book chapter wise in each subject by collect question paper pattern and questions from old question papers and from question bank.
- ✓ Make a weekly timetable with 16-18 hours study plan every day.
- ✓ Take weekly tests in the college seriously and prepare with special attention.
- ✓ Interact with the teachers in the class to clear the doubts.
- ✓ Try to solve old question papers problems and problems collected from.
- ✓ Participate in any challenging examinations like Olympiad, Fellowship offering exams etc. which will provide an opportunity to get experience and enhance confidence in facing competitive exams.
- ✓ Discuss both with lecturers and friends about various opportunities to plan and build the career.
- ✓ Use the time and technology effectively to enhance knowledge, skills and experience.

5.2. Strategies to be followed by the Parents: The strategies the parents of such students to be followed based on changing family environment, parents dream, expectations, pressure, and worry.

- ✓ Choose a college which has earned the name in quality education which includes providing learning ambience and strict discipline on the campus.
- ✓ The college should have a well-planned teaching & learning model which attracts all stakeholders for achieving their dream.
- ✓ Since 11th and 12th standard education and performance in exams are important in career building, parents should be careful in deciding the course and the college.
- ✓ See that your ward is properly motivated to set his/her goal and doing the continuous study as per the guidelines of teachers.
- ✓ Follow-up your ward to know his/her study plan and monitor to see that he/she has good friends who have the zeal for excellence.
- ✓ Avoid any activity or programs in the family which distract your ward attention from the study. The two years are very important in their life so that by every bodies help, they should be supported to reach their goal.

5.3. Strategies to be followed by the College:

- ✓ Set the Objective of the organization to get performance from the students
- ✓ Appoint best, experienced, innovative faculty members

- ✓ Choose best students who have interest in studies and capable of doing hard work
- ✓ Set the goal of both students and teachers
- ✓ Give the target to the students and teachers
- ✓ Provide organizational support in terms of infrastructure, facilities to do hard work.
- ✓ Arrange vigorous training by providing more contact hours with the students.
- ✓ Monitor the progress continuously by conducting exams periodically
- ✓ Arrange career planning information sessions and create a high competitive environment for the students.
- ✓ Fix accountability to avoid non-performance attitude and encourage the winners.

6. Strategies followed by an Experienced College – A case of Expert Pre-University College, Mangalore:

To face such critical situation, and support the students and the parents, Expert Pre-University College in Mangalore [54] developed a new innovative hard-work based training model called Seven to Seven (12 hours) Training Model. In the environment of enhanced competition, this new model is Student Centric. The paper contains the Core values of the new model, SWOC analysis, ABCD analysis, Stakeholders expectations, Institutional expectations, Student expectation, Teachers expectations and Parents expectations as a Case Study.

6.1 About Expert Pre-University College, Mangalore:

Expert P.U College has adopted a professional approach. It has a team of highly qualified, experienced and committed teachers It has a setup of well-equipped laboratories and state of art library which is completely computerized. The college offers phenomenal awareness for All India Competitive Examinations like JEE (Mains & Advanced), NEET, AFMC, AIIMS, JIPMER, and CET. The students are advised to make optimal use of these facilities. Expert Educational & Charitable Foundation firmly believes that a strong foundation in education is the surest way to the development of the Nation and Pre-university education is that crucial base. So, the college has developed a new systematic model of training the students with a view to shaping tomorrow's professionals. The success story of Expert Coaching Classes is very impressive. Started in a humble way in the year 1986 by Mr. Narendra L Nayak, a young engineering graduate, it began functioning from a small rented premises belonging to the Theosophical Society in the city. Beginning with a programme for imparting coaching to students appearing for the tough CA and ICWA examinations, the institute was successful in producing more than 300 chartered accountants within a short span of three years [54].

6.2 New Model Adopted By Expert College (Seven to Seven Intensive Class Room Training Model):

The college has adopted a new training model called “7 to 7 model” where admitted students are trained 12 hours per day from 7.00 am to 7.00 pm from Monday to Saturday and 6 hours on Sundays from 7.00 am to 1.00 pm. The training model contains preparing students for both PUC annual exams as well as Competitive exams for professional courses. The training is divided into two models as regular PU board syllabus training and competitive exam training. The students are about 20 months from June 1st to March 1st for continuously 20 months for two years PUC programme. The college gives vigorous training to the students and monitors their progress through the experienced teachers. With the motto of HARD WORK, the students are trained 12 hours per day. The college also provides printed study materials, popular branded

books for competitive exams and the textbooks published by the Expert Publisher-the publishing house of the college. Through a highly disciplined, continuous monitoring, and vigorous training model, and students are encouraged to do hard work in a competitive environment. The Seven to Seven model adopted by the Expert College has yielded an admirable result both in Board examination and in Competitive examinations as shown in Tables 1 to Table 3 (data is collected from college reports appeared in college magazines).

Table 1: Result of Last Three Years

Year	No. of Admission	No. of Pass and %	No. of students got $\geq 95\%$	No. of students got $\geq 90\%$	No. of students got $\geq 85\%$
2016	1059	1054 (99.53)	141	552	805 (78.02%)
2015	763	761 (99.48)	128 (17%)	404 (53.31%)	590 (77.53%)

Table 2: CET Top ranks

Year	Top ranks in CET	JEE Preliminary Qualified	KVPY Fellowship
2016	40 ranks from 50 Ranks	316/625	-
2015	41 ranks from 50 Ranks	71	14/1400

Table 3: Number Students scored 100/100 marks

Year	Physics	Chemistry	Maths	Statistic/CS	Biology
2016	80	59	98	23	29
2015	46	32	27	60	22

6.3 Stake Holders Expectation from New Model:

(i) Institutional Expectations:

- ✓ A unique good education training to the students who are chosen based on their performance in previous exams.
- ✓ A good discipline in the college campus and scheme of providing value based education.
- ✓ Vigorous training to the students through Seven to Seven model to get the best result.
- ✓ Continuous support & monitoring the students to get the best result.
- ✓ Best training from the top experienced teachers to fulfill the expectations of parents.
- ✓ To give exposure on various competitive entrance exams to plan en-cash better career.
- ✓ To improve the performance continuously to get the ideal result (all students score 100 marks in all subjects) and ideal professional placement (all students get admission to top level institutions in their desired areas).
- ✓ 100% attendance to maintain equality in training for every student.

(ii) Student Expectations:

- ✓ Best training by qualified and experienced teachers.
- ✓ Good and lovely ambience for learning.
- ✓ Highly competitive environment for studies
- ✓ Good academic support through study materials, question bank solutions, weekly exams, and quick evaluation results to check the progress.
- ✓ Continuous monitoring by the teachers to clear any and every doubts in the subjects.
- ✓ Encouragement and motivation to achieve high scores in all subjects.

(iii) Teachers Expectations:

- ✓ The students are assets of the institution and they were best performers in this region. They deserve the best.

- ✓ Based on a planned and monitored study, students will show the best performance which will give good name and fame to the teachers and the college.
- ✓ The super-performance of the students increases the brand of the college and hence demand so that the faculty members who are responsible for such result will also get happiness and professional growth.

(iv) Parents Expectations:

- ✓ Every parent thinks that my ward is an intelligent and hard worker. He needs the best college at any cost to realize my dream.
- ✓ With good college, good teachers, good environment and with good classmates, he can do an exceptional performance to fulfill his desire.
- ✓ The college with its pedagogy and dedicated teachers motivate and guide my ward effectively so that he will score very high marks and get entry to top ranked institutions for further study.
- ✓ By admitting my ward to a reputed college, I can relax and focus on my works.

7. SWOC Analysis of New Model:

The seven to seven college study model is analysed for its strength, weakness, opportunities, and challenges using SWOC analysis model [14, 55].

(i) Strengths of the Model:

- ✓ Supports hard work.
- ✓ Gives confidence for parents
- ✓ Creates brand value to the college
- ✓ Adds name and fame to the lecturers
- ✓ Increases admission demand
- ✓ Assured success to the students and the college
- ✓ Students are studying 12 hours in the college per day so that can score maximum possible marks in each subject.
- ✓ Enhanced confidence to the students to face competitive entrance exams.
- ✓ Ensured best performance from the students.
- ✓ Positive public opinion.

(ii) Weakness of the Model:

- ✓ Students are made to work 12 hours per day which may affect the morale
- ✓ Only self-motivated hard workers can sustain and perform better.
- ✓ The co-curricular and extra-curricular activities are not supported.
- ✓ Admission is based on merit only so that low performers in previous exams will not get the opportunity.
- ✓ Since the college has to provide service through experienced faculty during 12 hours per day and 6 hours on Sundays, the model is costly and not affordable for poor people.

(iii) Opportunities of the Model:

- ✓ Assured performance by the students due to associated hard work.
- ✓ High competitive environment.
- ✓ Opportunity to interact with experienced faculty, and with highly focussed students.
- ✓ Enhanced knowledge, skills, and competence.
- ✓ Students study well with teachers compared to their study with their parents.
- ✓ The model provides confidence to the parents.

(iv) Challenges of the Model:

- ✓ Students have to attend classes regularly without leave.

- ✓ Sitting 12 hours in the classes daily about 20 months is really a challenge for students.
- ✓ Arranging classes / tuitions 12 hours per day by arranging effective teachers.
- ✓ Achieving success through students performance in final exams and competitive exams.
- ✓ Developing simple but systematic study materials related to both board curriculum and Competitive exam curriculum.

8. ABCD Analysis of New Model:

The seven to seven college study model is also analysed using ABCD analysis by listing its Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages [56 - 60].

(i) Advantages:

- ✓ Parents can be tension free.
- ✓ Once admitted, students are forced to do hard work.
- ✓ Students will not divert their attention through bad friends and waste their times
- ✓ Fixing the goal, setting the target, continuous monitoring throughout till achieving the goal.
- ✓ This hard work model developed and offered by the college gives the expected success.

(ii) Benefits:

- ✓ Parents can realize their dream through assured success in scoring good marks by their ward.
- ✓ Students can fulfill their ambition of choosing their planned profession through monitored hard work.
- ✓ Teachers can get name and fame for their efforts by getting the good result in their subjects.
- ✓ The college improves its brand image and increases its admission demand.
- ✓ The society gets innovators and understands that there is no alternative for planned hard work.

(iii) Constraints:

- ✓ Convincing the parents about new model initially.
- ✓ Setting the goal and preparing the students for hard work in the college from seven to seven every day.
- ✓ Arranging the effective teachers for 12 hours training without boring.
- ✓ Providing competitive study material to the students.
- ✓ Developing continuous evaluation system to monitor the progress of individual students.

(iv) Disadvantages:

- ✓ Very challenging model.
- ✓ Pressure on achieving the exceptionally good result.
- ✓ Chances of students revolt to accept such model even if parent support it.

9. Conclusion:

By means of properly planned hard work and determination to achieve, a college can create an innovative model for the students to face the effects of changing the curriculum from the state level to the national level. Students can perform the best in both board and competitive exams, by setting their goal, fixing their target, supporting to study long hours in every day, monitoring and guiding through experienced and dedicated teachers, and finally through accountability. The innovative hard work based seven to seven student-centric learning model developed and implemented by Expert

Pre-University College, Mangalore yielded the desired result and became an attractive model in education.

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